

СЎЗ САЊАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

7 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 7, НОМЕР 1

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 7, ISSUE 1

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА | INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

№1 (2024) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9297-2024-1>

Бош муҳаррир:
Тўхтасинов Илҳом
п.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:

Главный редактор:
Тухтасинов Илхом
д.п.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Заместитель главного редактора:

Editor in Chief:
Tuhtasinov Ilhom
DSc. Professor (Uzbekistan)

Deputy Chief Editor

ТАҲРИРИЙ МАСЛАҲАТ КЕНГАШИ

Назаров Бахтиёр
академик. (Ўзбекистон)

Якуб Умарўғли
ф.ф.д., профессор (Туркия)

Алмаз Улви Биннатова
ф.ф.д., профессор (Озарбайжон)

Бокиева Гуландом
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Миннуллин Ким
ф.ф.д., профессор (Татаристон)

Махмудов Низомиддин
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Керимов Исмаил
ф.ф.д., профессор (Россия)

Жўраев Маматкул
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Куренов Рахиммаед
к.ф.н. (Туркменистон)

Кристофер Жеймс Форт
Мичиган университети (АҚШ)

Умархўжаев Мухтор
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Мирзаев Ибодулло
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Болтабоев Хамидулла
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Дўстмухаммедов Хуршид
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Лиходзиевский А.С.
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Сиддикова Ирода
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Шиукашвили Тамар
ф.ф.д. (Грузия)

Туробов Бекпулат
масбул котиб, PhD, доцент
(Ўзбекистон)

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ

Назаров Бахтиёр
академик. (Узбекистан)

Якуб Умар оглы
д.ф.н., профессор (Туркия)

Алмаз Улви Биннатова
д.ф.н., профессор (Азербайджан)

Бакиева Гуландом
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Миннуллин Ким
д.ф.н., профессор (Татарстан)

Махмудов Низомиддин
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Керимов Исмаил
д.ф.н., профессор (Россия)

Джураев Маматкул
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Куренов Рахыммаед
к.ф.н. (Туркменистан)

Кристофер Жеймс Форт
Университет Мичигана (США)

Умархаджаев Мухтар
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Мирзаев Ибодулло
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Балтабоев Хамидулла
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Дустмухаммедов Хуршид
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Лиходзиевский А.С.
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Сиддикова Ирода
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Шиукашвили Тамар
д.ф.н. (Грузия)

Туробов Бекпулат
отв. секретарь, PhD, доцент
(Узбекистан)

EDITORIAL BOARD

Bakhtiyor Nazarov
academician. (Uzbekistan)

Yakub Umarogli
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Turkey)

Almaz Ulvi Binnatova
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Azerbaijan)

Bakieva Gulandom
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Minnulin Kim
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Tatarstan)

Mahmudov Nizomiddin
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Kerimov Ismail
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Russia)

Juraev Mamatkul
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Kurenov Rakhimmamed
Ph.D. Ass. Prof. (Turkmenistan)

Christopher James Fort
University of Michigan (USA)

Umarkhodjaev Mukhtar
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Mirzaev Ibodulla
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Boltaboev Hamidulla
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Dustmuhammedov Khurshid
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Lixodzievsky A.S.
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Siddiqova Iroda
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Shiukashvili Tamar
Doc. of philol. scien. (Georgia)

Turobov Bekpulat
PhD Ass. prof. Senior Secretary
(Uzbekistan)

PageMaker | Верстка | Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

1. Nasimova Dilbar Baxodurovna FRANSUZ TILIDA BIR BO'G'INLI SO'ZLARNING OMONIMIK MUNOSABATLARIGA DOIR.....	5
2. Dalieva Madina Khabibullaevna PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF TRANSLATION OF LINGUISTIC TERMS AND CONCEPTS.....	11
3. Allaberdiyeva Durdona Gurbanmurat qizi QORAQALPOQ KORPUSINI YARATISHDA LINGVISTIK KORPUSLAR TAJRIBASIDAN.....	16
4. Аюпова Гулойим Бахтиёржон кизи ПАРАМЕТРЫ СООТНОШЕНИЯ ОКСЮМОРОНА И ВЕРБАЛЬНОЙ ИРОНИИ.....	22
5. Maxmaraimova Sh.T. S.A. ASKOLDOVNING “KONSEPT VA SO‘Z” MAQOLASI.....	28
6. Koziyeva Iqbol Kamiljonovna RUSSIAN ANTHROPNOMY DEVELOPMENT IN THE MODERN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE: ON THE EXAMPLE OF PERSONAL NAMES.....	40
7. Комила Мамадиёрова ПОЭТОНИМЛАРНИНГ БАДИИЙ-ЭСТЕТИК ФУНКЦИЯСИ.....	46
8. Холмурадова Зебинисо Шавкатовна ФРАНЦУЗ МАДАНИЯТИНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ ВА УЛАРНИНГ ЖАҲОН АДАБИЁТИГА КЎРСАТГАН ТАЪСИРИ.....	52
9. Xolbutayev G'ayratbek Oybek o'g'li O‘ZBEK XALQ OG‘ZAKI BADIYIY IJODIYOTIDA BETAKROR KULGI QO‘ZG‘ASHGA ASOSLANGAN SO‘Z SAN‘ATI.....	58
10. Mirsanov G'aybullo Qulmurodovich, Imamov Navruz Pattaqulovich INGLIZ VA O‘ZBEK TILLARIDA ITERATIVLIK ASPEKTUAL SEMANTIKASINI SHAKILLANTIRUVCHI TEMPORAL ADVERBIALLAR.....	64
11. Atamurodova Dilfuza Toshmurodovna KONSEPT TUSHUNCHASI VA UNING LINGVOKULTUROLOGIK TADQIQIGA DOIR MULOHAZALAR.....	69
12. Умида Хушвақтова ЗУЛФИЯ ҚУРОЛБОЙ ҚИЗИ АСАРЛАРИ ТИЛИНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОСЛИГИ.....	74
13. Садуллаева Нилуфар Азимовна, Мирходжаева Ферузахон Улугбековна АССОЦИАТИВНЫЙ ЭКСПЕРИМЕНТ НА ВОСПРИЯТИЯ ЦВЕТА У НОСИТЕЛЕЙ УЗБЕКСКОГО ЯЗЫКА.....	80
14. Комила Мамадиёрова ПОЭТОНИМЛАРНИНГ БАДИИЙ-ЭСТЕТИК ФУНКЦИЯСИ.....	89
15. Қосимова Мадина Зайнобидиновна БАХТ КОНЦЕПТИНИНГ ТАБИАТ БИРЛИКЛАРИ КЎЧИМИДА ИФОДАЛАНИШИ.....	95
16. Вазира Муродова “ОИЛА” КОНЦЕПТИГА ОИД ТИЛ БИРЛИКЛАРИ ТИЗИМИ.....	100
17. Nasrullaeva Nafisa Zafarovna CLASSIFICATION OF THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK GENDERLY MARKED PHRASEOLOGISMS DUE TO STRUCTURAL-SEMANTIC FEATURE.....	105
18. Ibragimova Lola Asatullo qizi TIBVIYOTGA OID EKVIVALENT (MUQOBIL) MAQOLLAR TAHLILI.....	110
19. Буриева Умида Абдумуниновна НЕПОЛНЫЕ ПРЕДЛОЖЕНИЯ И ИХ СОЦИОПРАГМАТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ В ДИСКУРСИВНОМ АНАЛИЗЕ.....	114

20. Хулкар Ҳамроева, Озода Мусаева БАДИИЙ МАТННИНГ ЛИНГВОПОЭТИК ТАҲЛИЛИ (Эрназар Рўзиматов асарлари мисолида).....	123
21. Умида Хушвақтова ЛИНГВОПОЭТИКА – ЯХЛИТ ФИЛОЛОГИК ТАҲЛИЛ МАЙДОНИ (Зулфия Куролбой кизи асарлари мисолида).....	131
22. Hayitov Shavkat Ahmadovich, Nasriddinova Shaxruza Nuriddinovna SHAYXIMBEK SUHAYLIY ALISHER NAVOIY TALQINIDA.....	139
23. Nasimova Muattar Xasanovna O‘QIB TUSHUNISH KO‘NIKMASINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA VAZIFAGA ASOSLANGAN TA’LIM TEKNOLOGIYASIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	149
24. Gulyamova Shahnoza Qahramonovna, Xudoyberdiyeva Filura Ziyadinovna NUTQ MADANIYATINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA EVFEMIZMLARNING AHAMIYAT.....	155
25. Petrosyan Nelya Valerevna KOMMUNIKATIV USUL ORQALI TANQIDIY FIKRLASHNI O‘RGATISH.....	160
26. Muhiddinova Gulchiroy Sadulloyevna YOZMA NUTQNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI.....	167
27. Abduraxmonova Nilufar, Latipova Gulasal KOMPYUTER LEKSIKOGRAFIYASIDA KORPUS TADQIQOT OBYEKTI SIFATIDA.....	171
28. Меликова Мартаба Нумоновна ЭСТЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ИДЕАЛЫ В ДУХОВНОМ НАСЛЕДИИ АЛИШЕРА НАВОИ.....	178
29. Ahmadova Umidaxon Shavkat qizi HUNARMANGLAR NUTQINING LINGVOMADANIY TAHLILI.....	186
30. Alimova Sevara Farkhadovna COLOR IDENTITY IN TRADITIONAL CHINESE CULTURE.....	193
31. Jo‘raxolova Bahora Qurbonboyevna NEMIS VA O‘ZBEK TILLARIDAGI MAQOLLARDA KONTSEPTUAL METAFORA TURLARINING TASNIFI.....	197
32. Абдуллаев Тигран Одил ўғли КРЕАТИВНОЕ МЫШЛЕНИЕ.....	203
33. Olimjonov Sarvarbek Abdusalom o‘g‘li ERIX MARIYA REMARKNING “ORTGA YO‘L” ROMANIDA URUSH MAVZUSI TALQINI.....	206

Nasrullaeva Nafisa Zafarovna

Doctor of philology, professor of
Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

CLASSIFICATION OF THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK GENDERLY MARKED PHRASEOLOGISMS DUE TO STRUCTURAL-SEMANTIC FEATURE

 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12746114>

ABSTRACT

The present article investigates English and Uzbek genderly marked phraseological units paying attention to structural-semantic signs of their gender component. Componential analysis gave chance to divide genderly marked phraseological units into 4 groups: 1) anthropometric words, which nominate men or women; 2) masculine and feminine names (anthroponyms); 3) kinship terms which denote family roles of men and women; 4) agentive nouns which denote professions which deal with definite gender. Theoretical content of the article can be proved by numerous examples of English and Uzbek phraseologisms chosen from trustful lexicographic sources.

Key words: genderly marked phraseological unit, gender component, anthroponym, agentive noun, kinship term, anthropometric word.

Насруллаева Нафиса Зафаровна

Филология фанлари доктори,
Самарқанд давлат чет тиллар институти профессори

ИНГЛИЗ ВА ЎЗБЕК ТИЛЛАРИДАГИ ГЕНДЕР БЎЁҚЛИ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЗМЛАРНИНГ СТРУКТУР-СЕМАНТИК ТАСНИФИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мазкур мақола инглиз ва ўзбек гендер бўёқли фразеологик бирликлар компонентларнинг структур-семантик белгиларининг тадқиқига бағишланган. Компонент таҳлил гендер бўёқли фразеологик бирликларни 4 та гуруҳга ажратди: 1) антропометрик сўзлар, яъни эркак ёки аёлни номланувчи лексемалар; 2) ўғил ва қизларнинг номлари (антропонимлар); 3) эркак ва аёлнинг оилавий ролларни ифодаловчи қариндошлик терминлар; 4) касб-хунарни, касбий фаолиятни, турли лавозимларни ифодаловчи агентив сўзлар. Мақоланинг назарий мазмуни ишончли лексикографик манбалардан танланган инглиз ва ўзбек фразеологизмлар билан далилланган.

Калит сўзлар: гендер бўёқли фразеологик бирлик, гендер бўёқли компонент, антропоним, агентив сўз, қариндошлик термини, антропометрик сўз.

Насруллаева Нафиса Зафаровна

Доктор филологических наук, профессор

Самаркандского государственного института иностранных языков

КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ АНГЛИЙСКИХ И УЗБЕКСКИХ ГЕНДЕРНО МАРКИРОВАННЫХ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЗМОВ ПО СТРУКТУРНО-СЕМАНТИЧЕСКОМУ ПРИЗНАКУ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Настоящая статья исследует английские и узбекские гендерно маркированные фразеологизмы английского и узбекского языков с обращением внимания на структурно-семантические признаки гендерного компонента в их составе. Компонентный анализ гендерно маркированных фразеологических единиц позволил выделить 4 группы гендерных компонентов в их составе: 1) антропометрические лексемы, т.е. лексемы, указывающие на денотат мужского или женского пола; 2) мужские и женские имена собственные (антропонимы); 3) термины родства, обозначающие мужчин и женщин по семейному положению; 4) агентивные существительные, обозначающие различные профессии, должности, звания, связанные с определённым полом. Теоретическое содержание данной статьи подтверждается многочисленными примерами английских и узбекских фразеологизмов, выбранных из достоверных лексикографических источников.

Ключевые слова: гендерно маркированная фразеологическая единица, гендерный компонент, антропоним, агентивное существительное, термин родства, антропометрическая лексема.

Gender studies of phraseological units, the use of linguistic means depending on belonging to a particular gender, and the reflection of national specifics of gender concepts in language are important tasks of world linguistics [3, pp. 22-28]. Phraseology reflects information related to the gender characteristics of the development of society [5, p. 230]. Therefore, the research of phraseological material from the perspective of gender and cognitive linguistics is of particular importance. Language is an important medium of information [12, p. 132]. A significant issue is the comparison of male and female stereotypes based on the phraseology of the English and Uzbek languages, the identification of gender asymmetries in both languages.

According to the fair statements of leading linguists, large-scale research is currently being conducted in world scientific centers within the framework of modern aspects, including cognitive linguistics, linguoculturology, linguistic worldview, comparative linguistics and intercultural communication [6, p. 12-14]; [4, p. 85]. Special attention is paid to the problems of communicative behavior of men and women in the process of communication [7, p. 112], determining the role of people's speech in identifying gender relations [8, p. 112], the development of a scientific and methodological basis for the comparative study of gender-colored units of different languages, the study of this phenomenon based on human imagination and national mentality.

Gender-marked phraseological units are figurative expressions of the language that fix and reflect the concepts of "male", "female" and ideas about these concepts [9]. A gender-marked phraseological unit does not always contain a gender component, which is sometimes completely absent from the structure of a gender-colored phraseology. Or, conversely, a phraseological unit containing a gender component does not nominate a man or a woman. How do you distinguish a gender-marked phraseology from a gender-neutral one? A gender-marked phraseology must necessarily contain a gender reference and characterize a man or woman. The difference between gender-marked phraseological units and gender-neutral units is particularly difficult, since in both languages there are enough phraseological units used in the characterization of both men and women: аччиғи бурнининг учиди туради – angry, nervous man; нозик табиат – capricious person, of delicate nature; нон термаган, ош термаган – as thin as a bone; a hard nut to crack – a firm person; fat as a pig – very fat; wooden head – stupid. The given examples present information about character, appearance, intellect of men and women without gender indexing.

The componential analysis of genderly marked phraseological units led to division of them into 4 main groups:

1. Anthropometric words, which denote male or female gender: man, woman, lady, boy, girl, Mr, sir, Miss, etc.

In the Uzbek language anthropometric words are: эркак – man; аёл (хотин) – woman; ўғил (бола) – boy; киз (бола) – girl; йигит – fellow; жаноб – Mister; хоним – lady; бек – noble man, etc.

There are examples of English and Uzbek phraseological units with anthropometric words: атала полвон – weak person; бекорчиларнинг беги – lazy person; бўз йигит – a young man; king for a day – short-term happiness; big boy – old friend; Prince Charming – prince from fairy tale, ideal husband; bread and butter miss – schoolgirl; one's best girl – beloved girl; a fine lady – showy woman, boasting woman [1, p. 432].

The group of anthropometric words in the Uzbek language also contains the word хотин, which has two meanings: 1) “woman”, 2) “wife”. In the meaning of “woman” it is used in the following phraseological units: хотин боши билан – being a woman; хотин киши – a woman, female. In the meaning of “wife” the word хотин is used in phraseological units which point at marriage or husband: хотин жаллоби – a man who has married and divorced for several times; хотин оши – marriage feats [2, p. 268].

In the following phraseologism there are two such words at once; king's man – the defender of English people (during fight for independence).

Even the English word goddess has gender meaning and denotes female: the goddess of corn – (myth.) the goddess of agriculture [11, p. 54].

English phraseology contains genderly opposite units: King's coat / Queen's coat – military coat; King's counsel / Queen's counsel – royal advocate; a man Friday – faithful assistant (boy) / a girl Friday – faithful assistant (girl); Mr. Right – future husband / Miss Right – future wife; a man of letters – writer, scientist / a woman of letters – woman-writer, female scientist; stag party – bachelors' company / hen party – girls' party; to play a man – to behave like a man / to play a woman – behave like a woman; master of situation – the master of situation (about independent man) [1, p. 600] / mistress of situation – the mistress of situation (about independent woman).

Some expressions can be differ in semantic aspect: a man of the world – experienced person / a woman of the world – married woman [10, p. 109].

Another group of phraseological units are formed by expressions with anthropometric lexeme gentleman, some of them actualize metaphorical meaning: the little gentleman in black velvet – mole; gentleman of the three outs – not stylish man; the gentleman in black – devil; gentleman (man) on condition – man in high position; gentleman in brown – bug; gentleman farmer – farmer-gentleman; gentlemen of the cloth – clergy; coloured gentleman – dark complexion [1, p. 368].

The word gentleman itself denotes good-natured man: one of Nature's gentlemen – one of common and good-natured people. In phraseological units the connotation can be varied from negative to positive due to the situation and contexts of usage.

With neutral connotation: the reverend gentleman – priest.

With positive connotation: fine gentleman – stylish, fashionable man; a gentleman (or man) of quality – noble man.

With negative connotation: gentleman of the pad – robber from main road; gentleman of fortune – pirate, swindler.

The word gentleman can also point at professional occupation of male person: gentlemen of the robe – lawyers, judges; walking gentleman – statist; gentleman's gentleman – footman, servant; gentleman in waiting – chamberlain; gentleman (или man) of virtue – art evaluator; gentleman at large – a man without a definite occupation.

The appeal to awarded member of Parliament is realized by the expression The Most Honourable gentleman, appeal to one member of Parliament to another – the honourable (and gallant) gentleman.

2. Male and female proper names, i.e. anthroponyms. It often happens that a proper name loses its onymic feature and acquires features of common names. Sometimes proper names in structure of

phraseological units doesn't denote a person: балойи Азим – skillful, talented, gifted; базми Жамшид – luxurious feast; ақли Салим – very intelligent, clever, smart; Хўжа Аҳропнинг моли – these things are not affordable to everyone [2, p. 271]; Jack and Jill – beloved couple; wife and husband, who love each other; the Blue Peter – to leave, to go away; Jack of all trades – a person who can do a lot of different work, “golden” hands; Jack Tar – English sailor; Tom fool – foolish; fool; round Jack – an item for hats.

There are many phraseological units with proper names in the Uzbek language as well: иш йўқ, Алим йўқ – to idle, to sit back, without any occupation; Алининг аламини Валидан олмоқ / Исонинг аламини Мусодан олмоқ – to express anger to another guiltless person; Али десанг, Бали дейди – to dispute, to bicker, to wrangle; Али хўжа – хўжа Али – it doesn't matter; жонини Жабборга бериб – with all strength.

3. English and Uzbek kinship terms, which denote men or women due to their family roles and kinship relations: father / ота; mother / она; son / ўғил; daughter / қиз; brother / ака; sister / опа, сингил; husband / эр; wife / хотин; uncle / тоға, амаки; aunt / хола, амма; grandfather / бобо; grandmother / буви; daughter-in-law / келин; son-in-law / куёв.

In both compared languages there are phraseologisms with kinship terms:

In Uzbek: онанг билан тенг – she is in your mother's age; она қизим – my dear (appeal to girls); опа-сингил тутинмоқ – to be called sisters; опа-ука тутинмоқ – to be called brother and sister; оппоқ дада – grandfather; отанг билан тенг – he is in your father's age; ота-онаси билан (бирга) қийналсин – may him grow with both parents; атала-ю аммам – weak, deadhead; келин туширмоқ – to marry son [2, p. 137].

In the English phraseology: Father Time – precious time; Father Christmas – Christmas Santa Claus; the mother of Parliaments – mother of Parliament, England; sworn brothers – called brothers; Sister Ann – faithful friend (girl); favourite son – political figure; the daughter of Eve – female; Aunt Sally – 1) name of the game; 2) the object of insult; teach one's grandmother to suck eggs – to teach experienced person to do smth he/she can easily cope with. It should be noted that phraseologisms with kinship terms may express meaning that doesn't belong to kinship or family relations.

4. Agentive nouns, denoting various professional occupations, duties, ranks, staff, associated with a definite gender. For instance, in English we have the following agentive nouns: lord, soldier, pilot, warrior, seaman, preacher / priest, fisher, guard, knight. Let's give the examples of phraseological units with such agentive nouns: guard of honour – awarded guard; like priest, like people – people of same unity have similar qualities; an old soldier – an experienced person; cub pilot – starting pilot; drop the pilots – to refuse a consultant; company gunmen – armed entrance security; feather-bed campaigner (soldier or warrior) – soldier in the rear; free companion – hired soldier; great seizer – sheriff.

Some phraseological units with agentive nouns don't denote masculine profession: have merchant's ears – to pretend not hearing; the cobbler must (should) stick to his last – every person should know his place.

This group contains a number of expressions with archaic lexeme knight: knight adventurer – travelling knight; knight of the carpet – knight that got his position not on the battle field but by bowing his head in court; knight of the vapour – heavy smoker; knight of the whipping-post – swindler, scammer, rogue; Knight of the Round table – one of King Arthur's knights; the knight of the shire – member of parliament or county.

The phenomenon of doubled meaning can be observed in the phraseological units with component knight, where agentive meaning is actualized due to description of means of work or object of professional activity: knight of the brush – painter; knight of the cleaver – butcher; knight of the grammar – school teacher; knight of the green cloth – gambler; knight of the knife – thief pickpocket, hustler, jostler; knight of the needle – tailor; knight of the pencil – writer, journalist; knight of the pestle – pharmacist, druggist; knight wagger – hired soldier, etc.

Agentive lexeme lord directly points at male person and his social status: the first Lord of the Admiralty – ministry of naval affairs; paper lord – officer-lord.

Phraseologism the great fisher of souls actualizes its meaning by metaphorical transformation: evil, devil.

In the Uzbek language there are less phraseological units with agentive nouns: ҳолвачининг тешасидек чакқон – very smart, resourceful person; подачининг оши – food from different products, modest food; мулла бўлмоқ – to be punished; кўз боғлағич – magician, wizard; карнайчидан нима кетди – бир пуф – it's very easy for him; бўзчининг мокисидек – very fussy, bustling.

As it is vivid from the given examples, most of agentive nouns deal with male professions and occupations.

The material of English phraseology states that lexeme man is used for a human in general. In the Uzbek language equivalent word is одам with meaning “human”. General nomination of a person can also be expressed by English word person and Uzbek words киши, инсон.

An interesting fact is that in the paremiology of the English language the personal pronoun “he” can be used in relation to a woman. Similarly, both a man and a woman can be nominated by the masculine possessive pronoun “his” and the pronoun “him, his”. In the process of analyzing gender-marked phraseological units with proper names, cases of using male names to characterize a person in general, without directly indicating gender, were also identified. Isolated cases of the use of “female” lexemes or names to designate a man were identified.

A number of English and Uzbek nouns in the structure of genderly marked phraseologism nominate a person in general and can be used both for men and women: Uzbek words дастёр, дайди, гадой, таниш, ошна, гувоҳ, кўшни, малай, меҳмон; English words: citizen, servant, liver, child, traveler, reporter, doctor, player, commoner, sleeper, etc.

Literature:

1. Кунин А. В. Англо-русский фразеологический словарь. – Изд. 3-е, испр., в двух книгах. – Москва: СЭ, 1967. – Т.1. – 738 с.; Т.2. – 739-1264 с.
2. Садыкова М. Краткий узбекско-русский фразеологический словарь. – Ташкент: Главная редакция Узбекской Энциклопедии, 1989. – 336 с.
3. Таджибаева А.А. Гендерный аспект стилистических приёмов // Преподавание языка и литературы. – Ташкент, 2009. – №3. – С. 22-28.
4. Хошимов Г.М. Концептуал семантика ва уни воқелантирувчи тил бирликларининг психоллингвистик тавсифи масалалари. // Филология ва маданиятлараро коммуникация: долзарб масалалар ва истиқболлар. Ўзбекистонда хизмат кўрсатган Фан арбоби, ф.ф.д., проф. А.А. Абдуазизов таваллудининг 80 йиллигига бағишланган илмий-амалий конференциянинг илмий мақолалар тўплами. – Тошкент, 30 апрель 2018. – Б. 85-91.
5. Чутпулатов М.У. О понятиях «гендер» и «гендерология» // Иностранные языки в подготовке кадров для внешнеполитических и внешнеэкономических связей. Материалы научно-практической конференции. – Ташкент: УМЭД, 2007. – С. 229-233.
6. Ashurova D.U., Galieva M.R. Text Linguistics. – Tashkent: Turon-Iqbol, 2016. – 323 p.
7. Belenky M. F., Clinchy B. M., Goldberger N. R. and Tarule J.M. Women's Ways of Knowing. – New York: Basic Books, 2006. – 243 p.
8. Bolinger D. Meaning and form. – New York: Longman, 2007. – 312 p.
9. Ergasheva G.I. Applied linguistics: Terminology and Translation through gender discourse lens. – Tashkent: Navruz, 2018. – 154 p.
10. Nasrullaeva, N. Z. (2018). English-Russian-Uzbek dictionary of genderly marked phraseological units. Tashkent: Navruz.
11. Oxford Dictionary of Idioms. – Second edition. – Oxford: Oxford University press, 2004. – 340 p.
12. West Candace and Zimmerman Don. Doing gender. // Gender and Society. – 2003. - № 1. – P.125-151.

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

7 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 7, НОМЕР 1

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 7, ISSUE 1

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000